

Global Warming: Velocity and Acceleration of Change in Cumulative CO₂ Emissions

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Abstract

This publication introduces two parameters related to cumulative CO₂ emissions. The first parameter is “*Velocity of Change in Cumulative CO₂ Emissions*”, VCCO₂. This parameter represents an average annual change in cumulative CO₂ emissions and is expressed in ton of CO₂ per year.

The second parameter is “*Acceleration of Change in Cumulative CO₂ Emissions*”, ACCO₂, and is expressed in ton of CO₂ per year, per year (tCCO₂/y²).

These two parameters are in addition to the parameter “*Global Warming Rate*”, GWR [°C/y], and “*Global Warming Acceleration*”, GWA [°C/y²], described in the previous publication.

The velocity of change in cumulative CO₂ emissions, VCCO₂, is +35.33 GtCCO₂/y in the last 11 years, and the acceleration of change in cumulative CO₂ emissions, ACCO₂, is +0.559 GtCCO₂/y² in the last 31 years.

Glossary

Δ CCO ₂	actual annual changes in cumulative CO ₂ emissions, tCO ₂ /y
ACCO ₂	Acceleration of Change in Cumulative CO ₂ Emissions, annual changes in Velocity of Change in Cumulative CO ₂ Emissions, VCCO ₂ , determined as 31 years trendline slope of the annual changes in the cumulative CO ₂ emissions, tCO ₂ /y ² (ton CO ₂ per year per year)
Ave	average
BL	baseline
CCO ₂	global cumulative CO ₂ emissions according to publication [1] [2], CO ₂ emissions produced from fossil fuels and cement production only – land use change is not included, tCO ₂
CO ₂	emissions of Carbon Dioxide, CO ₂
GtCO ₂	Giga-ton of CO ₂ , 10 ⁹ ton, 10 ⁹ ton, 1,000,000,000 ton of CO ₂
GWA	Global Warming Acceleration, the annual change in the global warming rate, °C/y ² [3]
GWR	Global Warming Rate – average change in global surface temperature per year in the trendline period, °C/y [3]
OWID	Our World in Data – Internet site [1] [2]
Ref	reference
tCO ₂	ton CO ₂
TL	trendline
VCCO ₂	Velocity of Change in Cumulative CO ₂ Emissions, 11 years average of annual changes in cumulative CO ₂ emissions, tCO ₂ /y

Periods Applied for the Calculations

For determination of VCCO₂, 11 years periods are applied every 10 years for averages of the actual annual changes in cumulative CO₂ emissions.

For determination of ACCO₂, 31 years periods are applied every 10 years for trendlines of the actual annual changes in cumulative CO₂ emissions.

Formula

Formula 1 - Velocity of change in cumulative CO₂ emissions, VCCO₂
[GtCO₂/y]

$$\mathbf{VCCO_2 = Ave(\Delta CCO_2) [GtCO_2/y]}$$

The velocity of change, VCCO₂, is determined in this version as an 11 years average of the actual annual changes in cumulative CO₂ emissions.

Database of Global Cumulative Amount of CO₂

Table 1 - Database of global cumulative amount of CO₂

Source of data	OWID
Reference	[1] [2]
Baseline year	1749
From year	1750
To year	2020
Period, years	271
CO ₂ from fossil fuels	Yes
CO ₂ from cement production	Yes
CO ₂ from other sources	No
Other GHG	No
Land use change	No
Units	ton CO ₂
Resolution	1 ton CO ₂ /y

The database is from publication [1] [2], CO₂ emissions produced from fossil fuels and cement production only – land use change is not included.

Cumulative CO2 Emissions

Chart 1 - Cumulative CO2 emission [1] [2] [GtCO2]

Chart 2 - Annual changes in the cumulative amount of CO2 [GtCO2/y]

The change in 2019 was +36.70 GtCO2/y and in 2020 +34.81 GtCO2/y.

Velocity of Change in Cumulative CO2 Emissions

The velocity of change is determined in this version as 11 years average of annual changes in cumulative CO2 emissions.

Table 2 - Velocity of Change in Cumulative CO2 Emissions [GtCO2/y]

from year	to year	years	Center year	VCCO2 GtCO2/y
1750	1760	11	1755	0.01
1760	1770	11	1765	0.01
1770	1780	11	1775	0.01
1780	1790	11	1785	0.02
1790	1800	11	1795	0.02
1800	1810	11	1805	0.03
1810	1820	11	1815	0.04
1820	1830	11	1825	0.06
1830	1840	11	1835	0.10
1840	1850	11	1845	0.15
1850	1860	11	1855	0.26
1860	1870	11	1865	0.43
1870	1880	11	1875	0.67
1880	1890	11	1885	1.04
1890	1900	11	1895	1.54
1900	1910	11	1905	2.47
1910	1920	11	1915	3.28
1920	1930	11	1925	3.69
1930	1940	11	1935	3.95
1940	1950	11	1945	5.05
1950	1960	11	1955	7.50
1960	1970	11	1965	11.51
1970	1980	11	1975	17.49
1980	1990	11	1985	20.50
1990	2000	11	1995	23.65
2000	2010	11	2005	29.22
2010	2020	11	2015	35.33

Chart 3 - Velocity of Change in Cumulative CO2 Emissions [GtCO2/y]

Axis x is the center of the 11 years period applied for the calculation

Acceleration of Change in Cumulative CO2 Emissions

The Acceleration of Change in Cumulative CO2 Emissions is determined in this version as the 31 years trendline slope of the annual changes in the cumulative CO2 emissions.

The trendlines period applied in this version is 31 years and the starting points of the trendlines are every 10 years from 1750.

Table 3 - 31 years trendlines

i	Trendline	Trendline period			Trendline	
	ID	from	to	years	Center	
Symbol	TL(i)				CenterTL	Δy
Units		year	year	years	year	years
1	TL1	1750	1780	31	1765	
2	TL2	1760	1790	31	1775	10
3	TL3	1770	1800	31	1785	10
4	TL4	1780	1810	31	1795	10
5	TL5	1790	1820	31	1805	10
6	TL6	1800	1830	31	1815	10
7	TL7	1810	1840	31	1825	10
8	TL8	1820	1850	31	1835	10
9	TL9	1830	1860	31	1845	10
10	TL10	1840	1870	31	1855	10
11	TL11	1850	1880	31	1865	10
12	TL12	1860	1890	31	1875	10
13	TL13	1870	1900	31	1885	10
14	TL14	1880	1910	31	1895	10
15	TL15	1890	1920	31	1905	10
16	TL16	1900	1930	31	1915	10
17	TL17	1910	1940	31	1925	10
18	TL18	1920	1950	31	1935	10
19	TL19	1930	1960	31	1945	10
20	TL20	1940	1970	31	1955	10
21	TL21	1950	1980	31	1965	10
22	TL22	1960	1990	31	1975	10
23	TL23	1970	2000	31	1985	10
24	TL24	1980	2010	31	1995	10
25	TL25	1990	2020	31	2005	10

Following is an example of a trendline in the period 1990-2020, trendline ID=TL25.

Chart 4 - Annual change in cumulative CO2 emissions in period 1990-2020, TL25 [GtCO2/y]

The trendline formula for this period (TL25) is:

$$y = 0.559047036232x + 20.463928521193$$

$$a = 0.559047036232$$

The average acceleration of the change in cumulative CO2 emissions in the period 1990-2020 is 0.559 GtCO2/y² (=a), which is the slope of the linear trendline in this period (1990-2020).

Table 4 - Acceleration of Change in Cumulative CO2 Emissions
[GtCO2/y2]

Trendline ID	Trendline period		Trendline Center	Acceleration of change ACCO2	Change ΔACCO2/y
TL(i)	from year	to year	CenterTL year	a GtCO2/y ²	%/y
TL1	1750	1780	1765	0.00022	
TL2	1760	1790	1775	0.00031	4.1%
TL3	1770	1800	1785	0.00045	4.6%
TL4	1780	1810	1795	0.00078	7.1%
TL5	1790	1820	1805	0.00107	3.7%
TL6	1800	1830	1815	0.00144	3.5%
TL7	1810	1840	1825	0.00260	8.1%
TL8	1820	1850	1835	0.00461	7.7%
TL9	1830	1860	1845	0.00793	7.2%
TL10	1840	1870	1855	0.01384	7.5%
TL11	1850	1880	1865	0.02069	4.9%
TL12	1860	1890	1875	0.03036	4.7%
TL13	1870	1900	1885	0.04313	4.2%
TL14	1880	1910	1895	0.07149	6.6%
TL15	1890	1920	1905	0.08402	1.8%
TL16	1900	1930	1915	0.06363	-2.4%
TL17	1910	1940	1925	0.03997	-3.7%
TL18	1920	1950	1935	0.07113	7.8%
TL19	1930	1960	1945	0.17905	15.2%
TL20	1940	1970	1955	0.32203	8.0%
TL21	1950	1980	1965	0.49174	5.3%
TL22	1960	1990	1975	0.45232	-0.8%
TL23	1970	2000	1985	0.31655	-3.0%
TL24	1980	2010	1995	0.44828	4.2%
TL25	1990	2020	2005	0.55905	2.5%
Ave since 1900					4.5%
last 3					3.3%
					1.2%

Chart 5 - Acceleration of Change in Cumulative CO2 Emissions, ACCO2,
[GtCO2/y²]

Axis x is the center of the trendline period (2005 is the center of the 1990-2020 trendline period)

Change in Acceleration

Change in acceleration, dACCO2, is the slope of the ACCO2 trendline. The ACCO2 trendline formula is:

$$y = 0.020664973607x - 0.139577412972$$

The trendline slope is $0.0207 \text{ GtCO}_2/\text{y}^2/10\text{y} = 0.00207 \text{ GtCO}_2/\text{y}^3$ (GtCO_2/y^2 per year).

Table 5 - Annual change in Acceleration of Cumulative CO2 Emissions, dACCO2 [GtCO2/y³]

ACCO2 Linear Trendline Formula	$y = 0.020664973607x - 0.139577412972$	
Δy	10	y
TL a	0.020664974	
dACCO2	0.002066497	GtCO_2/y^3

Forecast of Cumulative CO2 Emissions using Velocity and Acceleration

In the following example, it is assumed that the current year is 2010, attempting to estimate cumulative CO2 emissions for the 2010-2020 decade.

The calculations are based on TL24 (1980-2010).

Table 6 - Starting point for the forecast

Trendline from	Trendline to	Starting year	CCO2	VCCO2	ACCO2	dACCO2
			GtCO2	GtCO2/y	GtCO2/y ²	GtCO2/y ³
1980	2010	2010	1,341	29.22	+0.4482834	+0.0020665

Table 7 - Forecast of cumulative CO2 emissions

	dACCO2	ACCO2	VCCO2	CCO2 TL	CCO2 actual	Δ	Δ
	GtCO2/y ³	GtCO2/y ²	GtCO2/y	GtCO2	GtCO2	GtCO2	%
2010	+0.00207	+0.44828	+29.22	1,341	1,341	+0.000	
2011	+0.00207	+0.45035	+29.67	1,371	1,376	+4.798	
2012	+0.00207	+0.45242	+30.12	1,401	1,411	+9.650	
2013	+0.00207	+0.45448	+30.58	1,432	1,446	+14.356	
2014	+0.00207	+0.45655	+31.03	1,463	1,481	+18.856	
2015	+0.00207	+0.45862	+31.49	1,494	1,517	+22.860	
2016	+0.00207	+0.46068	+31.95	1,526	1,552	+26.360	
2017	+0.00207	+0.46275	+32.42	1,558	1,588	+29.870	
2018	+0.00207	+0.46482	+32.88	1,591	1,625	+33.636	
2019	+0.00207	+0.46688	+33.35	1,625	1,662	+36.991	
2020	+0.00207	+0.46895	+33.82	1,659	1,697	+37.982	
Ave				1,496	1,518	+21.396	+1.4%

The procedure recommended in this work results in underestimation of the actual cumulative CO2 emissions by 1.4%, which means that the actual cumulative CO2 emissions exceeded the estimation based on previous decade data by 1.4%.

Chart 6 - Forecast and actual cumulative CO2 emissions for years 2010-2020 [GtCO2/y2]

Current Situation

Table 8 - Most recent data (June 2022) regarding cumulative CO2 emissions

Trendline		Starting	CCO2	VCCO2	ACCO2	dACCO2
from	to	year				
			GtCO2	GtCO2/y	GtCO2/y ²	GtCO2/y ³
1990	2020	2020	1,697	35.33	+0.5590470	+0.0020665

Changes in This Version

- Addition of change in acceleration of annual changes in cumulative CO2 emissions, dACCO2
- Addition of example of estimation of cumulative CO2 emissions in the last decade
- Editorial changes

References

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